

Scientific inequality and LMIC's: the international scientific community's duty of care

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Abstract

Scientific inequality is associated with gender and racial diversity in negatively influencing the development of research and scientific relations. Taking our cue from what is occurring within the international surgical community, we focus on some of the most significant initiatives aimed at overcoming these differences with particular reference to gender and race. Scientific differences across gender and race mainly burden researchers and members of the LMIC scientific community. A number of measures are proposed to reduce these inequalities and to ensure visibility and greater opportunities for inclusion in the life of societies and a greater presence in international scientific journals.

Keywords: *Inequalities, surgery. scientific community, LMIC.*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the differences in the management of surgical patients [1,2]. These differences have become an important part of the general debate on inequalities, especially those related to gender and race differences in health care [3,4,5]. This issue is compounded by a more insidious problem: the possibilities for African authors to access the scientific community both in terms of economic support [6,7] and in international scientific journals. A recent review estimated that out of a total of 2,196 articles, only 4.3% concerned Africa; out of 9,222 authors, only 3.2% had a primary African affiliation; and while the average number of authors per article was overall 4.2, only 3.1% of these authors were African [8]. This disparity, which has existed for some time [9], and has recently garnered more attention [10], risks compromising the validity of scientific research and deepening the furrow of diversity. The surgical scientific community can contribute to the more general battle to overcome inequality through renewed collaboration among scientific societies, associations, research bodies, or individuals affiliated with them. To date, such collaboration has developed in a consolidated form as relationships between societies, sharing of research experiments, participation in conferences, exchange of representatives in the respective conferences, and establishment of research or international committees. This type of collaboration requires substantial updating for the future.

The surgical experience

At the ESCP Annual Meeting in Dublin in 2015, a first meeting was held between surgical students and trainees, supported by their advisors, from seven European countries. That meeting was followed by the birth of EuroSurg, a European network of medical students and surgeons collaborating to conduct international multi-center studies [11,12]. The first study was published in 2018, [13] and by 2020, the membership had grown to 25 countries. Subsequently, the GlobalSurg Collaborative was born, which currently has more than 5,000 members from over 100 countries, and even more recently, CovidSurg, a platform for collaboration on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on surgery [14,15]. The six major English-speaking scientific societies of coloproctology (ACPGBI, RSM Coloproctology Section, ESCP, ASCRS, RACS Section of Colon and Rectal Surgery, CSSANZ) organize the Tripartite Colorectal Meeting to promote professional updating and international surgical relationships. Many societies offer young surgeons scholarships, residencies, and opportunities to participate in the conferences they organize. ISUCRS created a collaborative group that has recently completed a study on COVID-19 [16]. In this context, the following new initiatives should be considered: the creation of working groups common to several societies on guidelines (homogenization of diagnostic and therapeutic pathways), training (creation of a multidisciplinary pathway of familiarization with research and dissemination of its results), and relationships with companies that produce technologies (which technologies, their role, and how to use them).

The contribution of scientific societies

The overcoming of diversity and the intensification of scientific collaboration on the mentioned topics must include a greater involvement of the scientific community, especially in LMICs. There are three aspects of collaboration to be addressed within the scientific societies: a) sex differences, b) “racial” differences, and c) participation in clinical trials of LMICs, [17] which are significantly low for ethnic and racial minorities as well as for the structural aspects in science management [18]. However, some things are moving. At the 2018 and 2019 ASCRS Annual Scientific Meetings, two different regional societies assigned presentations on gender-related topics. Many scientific societies are concretely exploring this topic with great attention: the Message from ASCRS on Racism (<https://fascrs.org/news/a-message-from-ascrs-on-racism>); the American College of Surgeons Call to Action (<https://www.facs.org/about-ac/s/responses/racism-as-a-public-health-crisis>); initiatives such as Systemic Racism in Science at the AAAS Forum on Science and Technology Policy (<https://www.aaas.org/page/forum-science-technology-policy>); and the SUS Statement on Racism (<https://www.susweb.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/2020-SUS-Statement-on-Racism-and-Recent-Deaths.pdf>).

Regarding collaborations with LMICs, the scientific community should promote initiatives to be added to those already in place [19]. The WHO Global Initiative for Emergency and Essential Surgical Care (GIEESC) includes more than 2,300 members from 140 countries. (<https://www.who.int/initiatives/who-global-initiative-for-emergency-and-essential-surgical-care>). At the level of scientific inclusion, the role of Authoraid (<https://www.authoraid.info/en/>) in mentoring and creating facilitation pathways is significant. However, it has not led to greater participation in scientific societies that are not related to LMICs and, above all, do not have a structured collaborative link with scientific societies and their journals. A search in the ASCRS Directory revealed that currently only seven members are from African countries, while the ISUCRS Directory highlighted eight. Therefore, how can scientific societies make a concrete contribution in this area? The commitment to LMICs should take the form of promoting ways of collaborating with the aim of increasing knowledge and familiarity with medical-surgical pathologies and their treatment but, above all, through greater involvement of LMIC professionals and authors.

Perspectives

A real contribution to the development of scientific collaborations aimed at overcoming inequalities would occur by stimulating the presence of these authors in the life of the societies and creating dedicated sections in established international journals, starting with the official journals of the scientific societies, to host articles that bring the African reality and that of LMICs to international attention. The presence of scientific journals with African editorial boards and dedicated to Africans does not seem, however, to represent the right path but, rather, a new type of ghettoization. African Journals Online, the largest platform of African academic journals, hosts 529 journals from 33 African countries, with 170 on the topic of health. However, cross-checking them with the Scopus list of journals showed that of these, only 39 (23%) are listed as active. Is it therefore possible to adopt a different strategy in the process leading to the decision of whether to accept or reject an article in the major international scientific journals? Is it possible to adopt new evaluation parameters, even if unrelated to the current ones, that are useful for spreading knowledge about new realities? I think that a common goal should be to facilitate the process of bringing African colleagues closer to international standards for publication. This goal should not be seen as a favor or as aristocratic scientific benevolence but as a necessary approach to the reality that we all have the duty to know and make known.

To this end, a hypothesis of a mini guideline for selecting the articles to be published could include: a) the strip of the authors of the article must include at least one who has already published at least two articles in indexed journals or with IF ; b) the article must contain research or trials or in any case topics that refer to the local reality; c) before submission, the article must have been reviewed by a national scientific society or by a scientific committee of a university or national research body

Finally, the journal should create a section and a dedicated Editor that supports the final draft of the article after peer review, if necessary.

Conclusion

Many African countries and authors are struggling to free themselves from the colonial burden that still plagues their culture and reality. Scientific societies and journals can do a lot. Moreover, through a new kind of collaboration that extends beyond their institutional areas and enriches them, the principles of equality and global progress of which they are rightful bearers can be fully realized.

Notes:**Acronyms:**

ACPGBI, Association of Coloproctology of Great Britain and Ireland
 ASCRS American Society of Colon & Rectal Surgeons;
 CSSANZ Colorectal Surgical Society of Australia and New Zealand
 ESCP European Society of Coloproctology;
 ISUCRS International Society of University Colon and Rectal Surgeons;
 LMIC Low -Middle Income Countries;
 RACS Royal Australasian College of Surgeons
 RSM Royal Society of Medicine
 SUS Society of University Surgeons;
 WHO World Health Organizations

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